

IMPLEMENTATION OF CONSTRUCTION INPUT TO FRONT-TO-END PROCESS AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION IN SEMPHIL INFRA

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry has been an integral part of the manufacturing industry and several big businesses. They have been working hand in hand to execute engineering plans to implement business development, innovations, and manufacturing plants maintenance. This study was conducted to examine the level of implementation of construction input to front-to-end process and performance evaluation in SEMPHIL Infra. The total population was 150 respondents with a sample size of 88 respondents which were all direct selling agents in the mentioned locale. The study used a descriptive correlational design. The results showed that the implementation of the construction input was fully implemented, performance evaluation was very good, and there was a strong correlation between the two variables. The training and development programs appropriate to implement were project costs builder, tracker for work breakdown schedule, and baselining matrix for the quality of the materials. A program was proposed as the output of the study.

Keywords: *Construction input, Front-to-end construction process, Budget estimate, Construction works process and lead time, Performance evaluation, Quality of construction work*

INTRODUCTION

In the entrance of the modern era, the construction industry has been an integral part of the manufacturing industry and several big businesses. They have been working hand in hand

to execute engineering plans to implement business development, innovations, and manufacturing plants maintenance. In such partnership, it has come necessary to monitor the performance of the two industries and how they impact each other for their mutual benefit.

Implementation of construction input to front-to-end process involves directing and organizing each part of the project life cycle, from ideation to completion. It is a holistic practice with the goal of delivering projects on time and under budget. Front-to-end process is a complex discipline that requires addressing many important concerns, including scheduling, risk assessment, cost control and procurement. Project construction requestors interact with all team members involved in a construction project, from architects to owners to contractors

With over USD 180,000 million in total sales, the behemoth China State Construction Engineering once again tops the list in 2018, far ahead of its closest rivals, including Chinese countries like China Railway Group and China Railway Construction. The top three businesses in the ranking, which include China, Japan, and the United States, account for around 29% of the GPoC's total revenue but just 13% of its overall market value.

On the other hand, Japanese enterprises continue to increase their position in the Top 100 ranking, accounting for about 13% of total sales and reporting aggregate revenues of USD 179,763 million. Their total revenues climbed by 2%, while their market capitalization rose by more than 25%. Daiwa House Industry and Sekisui House, which are ranked 9th and 16th respectively and are primarily focused on homebuilding, are the two biggest Japanese corporations.

The current study intends to add to the body of knowledge on FEP by analyzing its application at SEMPHIL INFRA, a construction part of a manufacturing business. The analysis will pinpoint the difficulties and hindrances to FEP implementation in the organization and offer suggestions for bettering project planning and execution. This study will advance the construction industry's growth and development and offer insights that can be used by all kinds of enterprises and organizations by offering workable ways to enhance FEP implementation.

Moreover, this study will determine the relationship of construction in terms of front-to-end process, implementation, to the performance at SEMPHIL INFRA, budget, lead time, lack of execution, closed monitoring, quality and delays. Additionally, it will propose programs and development to address the existing limitations and problems in the industry found in the study and to contribute to the efficiency and effectiveness of the processes not only to the company but also to the stakeholders which will be further identified in the succeeding chapters.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to ascertain the contribution of construction to the front-to-end process, implementation, and performance at SEMPHIL INFRA, and more specifically, it resolved the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of:
 - 1.1 budget estimate,
 - 1.2 construction works (process) lead time, and
 - 1.3 construction quality of work?
2. What is the level of performance evaluation of the Construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of:
 - 2.1 lead time and
 - 2.2 quality of construction work?
3. Is there a significant relationship between level of implementation and performance evaluation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

For this study, an adapted research instrument in the form of a survey questionnaire was used to gather quantitative data from the respondents. The Likert scale allowed respondents to rate their level of agreement or disagreement with statements related to the implementation and evaluation of front-to-end planning in construction projects at SEMPHIL INFRA. The survey questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure its validity and reliability, and any necessary adjustments was made accordingly.

The population of this study was composed of the project construction requestors at SEMPHIL INFRA. Moreover, the G*power 3.1.9 will be utilized to identify the number of respondents. The population of the study was 150 respondents with an effect size of .30 and a power of 95%.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Level of implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of Budget Estimate

Indicators	X	VI
1. Involves all relevant requestors in the budget estimation process, such as architects, engineers, and subcontractors.	3.46	FI

2. Does not experience cost overruns due to inaccurate budget estimates.	3.12	I
3. Budget estimates compares to actual project costs accurate.	3.26	FI
4. Provide clear and detailed breakdowns of its budget estimates, including labor, materials, and overhead costs.	3.55	FI
5. Ensures that its budget estimates align with its clients' financial constraints and expectations.	3.42	FI
General Assessment	3.36	FI

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Implemented (FI)
2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Implemented (I)
1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Moderately Implemented (MI)
1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Not Implemented (NI)

Table 1.2
Level of implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of construction works (process) lead time

Indicators	X	VI
1. Communicates project requirements to the project team effectively.	3.50	FI
2. Demonstrate strong leadership skills when managing the project team.	3.54	FI
3. Has a good understanding of the technical aspects of construction work, such as building codes, engineering principles, and construction materials.	3.53	FI
4. Prioritizes the safety of the project team and the public during construction work.	3.74	FI
5. Ensures that construction work is completed on time and within budget.	3.29	FI
General assessment	3.52	FI

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Implemented (FI)
2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Implemented (I)
1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Moderately Implemented (MI)
1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Not Implemented (NI)

Table 1.3
Level of implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of construction quality of work

Indicators	X	VI
1. Ensures that construction work is completed on time and within budget.	3.30	FI
2. Prioritizes safety in its construction work practices and procedures.	3.74	FI

3. Ensures quality control in its construction work, including materials selection, workmanship, and compliance with regulations and standards. 3.51 FI

General assessment 3.52 FI

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Implemented (FI)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Implemented (I)
 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Moderately Implemented (MI)
 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Not Implemented (NI)

Table 2.1
Performance evaluation of the Construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of lead time

Indicators	X	VI
1. Estimates the lead time required for construction projects, from planning to completion accurate.	3.28	VG
2. Has a process in place for monitoring and adjusting lead time estimates based on actual project progress.	3.20	G
3. Communicates lead time estimates to stakeholders, including clients, subcontractors, and project team members.	3.30	VG
4. Actively seeks feedback from stakeholders regarding the accuracy and usefulness of its lead time estimates.	3.26	VG
General assessment	3.26	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G)
 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

Table 2.2
Performance evaluation of the Construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of quality of construction work

Indicators	X	VI
1. Delivers high-quality construction work, with minimal defects and rework.	3.34	VG
2. Has a process in place for monitoring and evaluating the quality of its construction work, such as through inspections, testing, and feedback from requestors.	3.30	VG
3. Trains and supports its project team members to ensure they have the knowledge and skills to deliver high-quality construction work.	3.43	VG
4. Uses high-quality materials and equipment in its construction work, and how does it ensure their quality and reliability.	3.47	VG
5. Communicates and address quality issues or concerns raised by stakeholders, including clients,	3.39	VG

subcontractors, and project team members.

General assessment	3.39	VG
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Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G)
 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

Table 3
Significant Relationship Between the Implementation of construction input to front-to-end process and Performance evaluation of the Construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFR at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors

Implementation of construction input to front-to-end process	Performance	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Budget Estimate	Lead time	.642**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Quality of Construction	.592**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Construction works	Lead time	.726**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Quality of Construction	.744**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Quality of work	Lead time	.648**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Quality of Construction	.676**	.000	Significant	Reject ho

Table 4
Program that may be proposed

Key Result Area	Objectives	Program/Activity	Time Frame	People Involved	Success Indicator
Budget Estimate	to help the project managers to make realistic forecasts on the budget and expenses.	project cost builder with built-in analytics and reporting tools	Q3 2024	Project managers	100% realistic budget estimates

Construction Works	To ensure that managers are allocating resources well and identifying who works for what within the project team	a tracker for work breakdown schedule (WBS) based on structured Gantt chart on phases of the project	Q2 2024	Project managers, construction workers	100% of construction works are allocated properly and deadlines are met on time
Quality of Work	To have a checklist for determining the quality of inputs or materials to be used	baselining matrix for the quality of materials	Q1 2024	Project managers, construction workers	95% of materials are of high quality and all the people are skilled in their work areas

DISCUSSION

The level of the implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of Budget Estimate was Fully Implemented as shown in the general assessment of 3.36. Provide clear and detailed breakdowns of its budget estimates, including labor, materials, and overhead costs. which yielded the highest mean score of 3.42 and was interpreted as Fully Implemented. On the other hand, the Does not experience cost overruns due to inaccurate budget estimates received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.12 and interpreted as Implemented.

These figures affirm that all necessary practices concerning budget and the detailing of the expenditure for the construction project are fully implemented. The proper tracking of budget and resources is an important project management consideration that managers and leadership should consider. It will shed light on the capacity of completing the construction work based on the plan and the budget allocated for it. The construction input in terms of budget estimates, including labor, materials, and overhead costs would visualize how the project can be completed based plotted figures of costing and itemization. This important practice among requestors would ensure the project success that eliminates waste, ensures budget optimization and eliminates the costs or expenses.

This is consistent with what Liu et al. (2021) asserted that the budget aspects would define how the construction project can stay within the baseline. Studies have identified inadequate planning, lack of resources, and insufficient communication as barriers to project implementation, while effective planning, communication, and allocation of resources can act as facilitators to project implementation. Additionally, the use of innovative technology such as BIM, effective project requestor engagement, and external factors such as government regulations and economic conditions can also act as facilitators to project implementation. The successful implementation of construction projects requires careful

consideration of these factors and the adoption of appropriate strategies to overcome barriers and leverage facilitators to improve project performance.

Meanwhile, the lowest item in the distribution refers to not experiencing cost overruns due to inaccurate budget estimates. A common misconception about budget in the project management is that the project can be strictly executed or implemented based on plan. There are occurrences of budget overruns since there are circumstances in the project lifecycle that are not foreseeable, or when it can be foreseen, cannot be avoided. These circumstances would definitely use up or utilize budget that is not initially laid out. The problems and concerns of the project team would now be to address such contingent situation of spending for items which are not primarily allocated for. The construction input thus serves a manifestation to overcome contingent problems in the delivery of patches or resolutions for problems and concerns.

Tran et al. (2019) carefully asserted how budget is being managed based on actual figures and tracking to identify any problems and areas of concern. This will avoid budget overruns which seemingly is a common challenge in construction projects, caused mainly by inaccurate cost estimates, changes in project scope, and unexpected project risks, which can lead to delays, reduced quality, and damage to project requestors reputations. Several approaches have been identified to mitigate budget overruns in construction projects. The use of value engineering, risk management practices, and collaborative approaches such as integrated project delivery and lean construction has been found to be effective in reducing project costs while maintaining project success certainty.

Essentially, the budget considerations in the project would initially dictate how the resources were effectively and efficiently managed. This is the primary thing that project teams should be guarding. While construction projects involve various complexities, the budget has to be guarded. It must take note of contingent situations and external factors that may increase expenditure. External factors such as weather conditions, material availability, and labor productivity can also cause delays (Nguyen et al., 2019). The impacts of project delays on project performance can be significant, including cost overruns, disputes, and reduced productivity, as well as affecting client satisfaction and reputation.

The level of the implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of construction works (process) lead time was Fully Implemented as shown in the general assessment of 3.52. It was determined that the item Prioritizes the safety of the project team and the public during construction work yielded the highest mean score of 3.74 and was interpreted as Fully Implemented. On the other hand, the Ensures that construction work is completed on time and within budget received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.29 and interpreted as Fully Implemented.

Based on the distribution, the foremost item is concerned about safety and security. In all construction projects, the first objective is ensuring that all employees and members of the project team are not put in danger. With the physical and exhaustive line of work of personnel in construction which requires rigorous work, the project managers are tasked to make guidelines and protocols to maintain the safety of everyone. Being able to complete

the project on time and on budget is just a secondary objective since the underlying and highly compelling goal is to keep everyone safe during the course of all the activities of the project.

According to a study by Singh and Bawa (2020), some of the key challenges include inadequate project planning and management, shortage of skilled labor, safety concerns, and environmental issues. Poor project planning and management can lead to project delays, cost overruns, and reduced project quality, while the shortage of skilled labor can result in a decline in project quality and productivity. Safety concerns can cause accidents leading to injuries, fatalities, and property damage, leading to project delays, increased costs, and reduced project quality. These are items that need to be avoided by making sure that construction inputs are supportive of the objectives of the construction project.

On the other hand, the item with the lowest mean score pertains to ensuring that the project is completed within the budget and the time allocated for it. This cannot be a guarantee for every construction project because adjustments would always need to be made based on emergent and contingent situations. The budget is sometimes lacking due to patches and resolutions that need to be carried out to avoid causing bigger problems. The lead time can be minimized or improved, but it cannot guarantee that deliverables are always completed based on the Gantt chart. There are several adjustments on the timeframe and the pacing of the results before the project gets completed. It can be a usual thing for construction projects but implementation of construction input can help address the underlying challenges on this.

Al-Ghafri et al., (2019) offered a parallel observation on the importance of project planning in construction projects and suggest the effective communication and collaboration among project requestors. Thus, importance of effective project planning ensure that the project is completed within the allocated time and budget while meeting the client's or requestor's requirements. This ensures that the project team has cognizance of the materials aspects concerning time and accomplishing the activities within the specified period.

It was inferred from the discussions that considerations on the project aspects involving construction works and process lead time has more rigid and structured basis compared to budget. While the process would essentially determine the rate of completion of the deliverables, it would also have far-reaching effect on the budget and timeline. Streamlining the process and making sure that redundant steps are eliminated would definitely introduce savings in both money and time. The construction input thus is a tool that may be used to mitigate the impacts of project delays, strategies such as risk management and mitigation in the project delivery.

The level of the implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of construction quality of work was Fully Implemented as shown in the general assessment of 3.52. It was determined that the item Prioritizes safety in its construction work practices and procedures yielded the highest mean score of 3.74 and was interpreted as Fully Implemented. On the other hand,

the Ensures that construction work is completed on time and within budget received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.30 and interpreted as Fully Implemented.

The distribution of items under construction quality of work offered that same insights as that of construction process lead time. It cannot overly underscore the importance of safety of the project team members. To reiterate, being able to complete the project on time and on budget is just a secondary objective since the underlying and highly compelling goal is to keep everyone safe during the course of all the activities of the project. The importance of safety in the construction work is very much aligned in the production of quality output for the construction work. The safety guidelines and parameters put in place by the project managers make the work efficient and thus has strong increments on time and budget.

Munier and Skitmore (2019), opined that safety is the primary baseline of producing quality output for the project. It is considered as the primary indicator of the success of the project that no employee was harmed or injured. This is a one hundred percent target on a daily basis which would not afford any compromise. Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been identified as an effective approach to measure project progress and success by monitoring project schedule, cost, quality, and safety performance. It is essential for construction project managers to choose the most appropriate method or combination of methods based on the project's objectives and requirements to ensure meeting budget and time objectives while maintaining the safety and security of everyone.

The lowest item in the distribution is similar to the one that was offered in construction process lead time which concerns the certainty that the project is completed within the budget. To repeat, this cannot be a guarantee for every construction project because adjustments would always need to be made based on emergent and contingent situations. The budget is sometimes lacking due to patches and resolutions that need to be carried out to avoid causing bigger problems. The lead time can be minimized or improved, but it cannot guarantee that project deliverables are completed on time and within the budget allocated for it.

Consistent with these insights, effective project planning is crucial for successful construction projects, as it helps ensure that the project is completed within the allocated time and budget while meeting the client's or requestor's requirements. Several studies have emphasized the importance of project planning in construction projects, with poor project planning identified as a significant factor affecting project success (Al-Ghafri et al., 2019).

Under the same framework of project management, the front-to-end process requires performance evaluation. This assessment strategy refers to the extent to which the construction input contributes to the success of the project based on its ability to meet its goals and objectives. What the construction input can offer to ensure project success can variably be measured or evaluated by structured metrics. The level of performance evaluation of the construction input can be gauged in terms of lead time and quality of

construction work. These constructs are presented in the two succeeding distributions of the mean scores.

The level of the performance evaluation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of lead time was Very Good as shown in the general assessment of 3.26. It was determined that the item communicates lead time estimates to stakeholders, including clients, subcontractors, and project team members yielded the highest mean score of 3.30 and was interpreted as Very Good. On the other hand, has a process in place for monitoring and adjusting lead time estimates based on actual project progress received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.20 and interpreted as Good.

It was inferred based on the findings that the proper cascading of information and insights based on construction inputs allows lucid flow of project delivery status. It would inform the stakeholders about the completion status and pacing of the items that need to be delivered within a specific timeframe. It helps the project team to make possible adjustments in order to keep up with the demands of the time. The delivery timeframe is therefore visualized by way of the tracking methods and strategies put in place by the project management. The communication between the members would always be significant to ensure the project success, so as to drive synergy, collaboration and integrated work for all stakeholders.

Effective project management skills, team communication, and leadership have been identified as critical factors affecting project success. Additionally, stakeholder or requestor management has been highlighted as an important factor in project success, with effective stakeholder or requestor management improving project success and reducing project risks. The use of innovative technology, such as BIM and AI, has also been identified as a crucial factor in improving project success. BIM can improve project visualization, coordination, and communication among project stakeholders, while AI can improve project scheduling and resource allocation (Zhang et al., 2019).

On top of this, communication can be enhanced by collaborative planning processes which have emerged as a key factor in successful construction project management, with numerous studies highlighting its potential benefits. Collaborative planning involves the active involvement of project stakeholders, such as owners, designers, contractors, and subcontractors, in the project planning and decision-making process, leading to increased communication and coordination among stakeholders.

Meanwhile, the lowest item in Table 2.1 refers to having processes in adjusting lead time estimates based on actual project progress. This is important for the project team, but it is rather difficult to perform. The project management team is just considered a steward of the time and the budget, they do not always have the luxury of deciding when or how to adjust the deliverables and the time frame. Project management principles have dictated that such adjustments should be made still within the light of the allowable threshold of the construction project delivery.

Nevertheless, effective leadership can promote team motivation and commitment, leading to improved project performance. Additionally, team communication promotes trust and

understanding among project team members, leading to improved project performance, while poor communication can result in project failure. Leadership involves setting clear project objectives, providing guidance and support, and promoting collaboration and communication among team members, whereas team-building activities aim to promote team bonding, trust, and communication, ultimately leading to improved team cohesion and project performance.

The level of the performance evaluation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors in terms of quality of construction work was Very Good as shown in the general assessment of 3.39. It was determined that the item Uses high-quality materials and equipment in its construction work, and how does it ensure their quality and reliability yielded the highest mean score of 3.47 and was interpreted as Very Good. On the other hand, has a process in place for monitoring and evaluating the quality of its construction work, such as through inspections, testing, and feedback from requestors received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.30 and interpreted as Very Good.

It implies that the utilization of high quality input of production and the employment of good quality of items will ensure the quality of construction work. While the industry would rely on the labor and materials, there cannot be any question on the mastery and skills of the laborers. It has to be ensure that the materials are of good quality, the equipment are in working condition. The results of the construction project would highly rely on the manner by which the materials are selected, sources and shipped from the end of the supplier to the site of the project. There has to be quality assurance and inspection processes that must be prepared for this.

Generally, factors have influenced the success of construction projects such effective stakeholder or requestor management, project visualization, coordination, and communication among project stakeholders. Also challenge is inevitable in the construction industry such skilled labor, safety concerns, and environmental issues (Singh & Bawa, 2020). Furthermore, implementation barriers and facilitators in construction projects are needed and developed to minimize and had careful consideration for the risk factors and the adoption of appropriate strategies to overcome barriers and leverage facilitators to improve project performance.

Meanwhile, the lowest concurrence was observed on the item that the construction project employs process in place for monitoring and evaluating the quality of its construction work, such as through inspections, testing, and feedback from requestors. This operational procedure would have an opportunity of enhancing the cooperation and collaboration between the members of team. While quality assurance is important, the metrics and key performance indicators for this have to clearly mapped out. It may begin from integrating within the construction inputs framework some checklists on the aspects and work items that has to be inspected or monitored based on specific baselines for control.

Several methods and approaches for project evaluation and performance measurement have been proposed in the literature for construction projects. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been identified as an effective approach to measure project progress and

success by monitoring project schedule, cost, quality, and safety performance. The use of earned value management has also been proposed as an effective approach to measure project performance by integrating project scope, schedule, and cost to provide a comprehensive assessment of project performance. Benchmarking, risk management, and other methods have also been suggested to evaluate and measure project performance (Munier & Skitmore, 2019).

There was a significant high positive correlation between the Implementation of construction input to front-to-end process and Performance evaluation of the Construction input to front-to-end process shown in the probability values of .000 which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus reject the null hypothesis. This implies that the more the construction input to front-to-end process is implemented, the higher the performance of the Construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors.

From the distribution in Table 3, the highest extent of relationship was recorded between the implementation of construction input to front-to-end process in terms of construction works and its quality. This affirms that the extent of performance of the work would have the natural tendency to increase the quality of work. The success of the construction project has reliance on the performance of the workers and project team in delivering within the specific time and budget.

Aside from this, it was determined as well, that lowest extent of association was observed between the implementation of construction input to front-to-end process in terms of budget estimate and quality of construction. The constraints on the budget when it was not justified on the outcomes will have an impact to the quality of construction work. When there are compromises or adjustments on the budget, the quality of work would also be undermined. There is direct relationship or increment between the amount of budget allocated for the purpose and the quality of work or the outcome of the subject construction project.

Fernández-Sánchez et al. (2019), similarly identified association between the quality of work and performance evaluation resting on the capacity of the project management to oversee the aspects of the work. Furthermore, to ensure project success in construction, it is crucial to implement best practices in project management. In sum, effective risk management, including identification, assessment, and management of project risks, has also been identified as a crucial best practice that can improve project planning, scheduling, and resource allocation, leading to improved project performance and efficiency. Effective communication and collaboration among project stakeholders are another critical best practice that can promote teamwork, coordination, and problem-solving, leading to improved project performance and efficiency.

The output in the study may be created as an in-house development or project to aid the project managers in tracking and consolidation of various aspects such as targets, budget, resources and deadlines. The project cost builder may help in the proper administration of expense-related tracking. The tracker for WBS may be tapped to oversee and manage the time-related aspects. Finally, the baselining matrix may be designed dependent on the policies and requirements of the construction company. These tools will help for project-

related implementation activities, control and performance evaluation aligned with Front-to-End Process.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The level of implementation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors was fully implemented. It was identified that the budget estimates, construction work lead time and quality of work are substantially integrated as construction inputs that harness an effective front-to-end process.
2. The level of performance evaluation of the Construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA as assessed by the requestors was evaluated as very good. It was a manifestation that evaluating the lead time and outcomes of the construction project are augmented on industry-relevant and time-tested project delivery efficiency.
3. There is significant relationship between level of implementation and performance evaluation of the construction input to front-to-end process at SEMPHIL INFRA. The strong correlation between these two variables establishes the certainty of addressing the challenges encountered in terms of budget and time allocation and enhances the extent of delivering project tasks in the construction industry.
4. Based on the result of the study, the outputs that may be presented to the stakeholders are project costs builder, tracker for work breakdown schedule (WBS) and baselining matrix for the quality of materials. These can be utilized to improve the overall project turnout and success. Additionally, to provide a valid and reliable representation of the expected costs of a construction project, it should include a detailed breakdown of all the costs associated with the project. Moreso, to accomplish the project objectives and create the required deliverables, tracker for work breakdown schedule (WBS) and baselining matrix for the quality of materials should be considered and organized using visual project representation.

Recommendations

Consistent with the findings and the conclusions presented, the researcher aims to provide the following recommendations to the stakeholders and project managers. The points for improvement involving the quality of work alongside budget and time efficiency needs to be given concentration. The following recommendations are therefore conveyed for the parties of interest as well as the future researchers in project management:

1. Project managers and team members in construction industry may focus on enhancing the communication channels. This will entice them to work hand in hand so as to achieve the targets of the project and the objectives of the organization and the client.
2. Project managers may increase their level of utilization of trackers, dashboards and reporting tools to overcome budget and time constraints. These challenges may be addressed by making informed decisions on aspects relating to staffing, resource allocation,

negotiation and cost analysis. They can also gain insights that are data-driven with these kinds of analytics strategies.

3. The outputs that were proposed in the present study may be harnessed from free sources so as to cut on expenses. Training programs online may also be exhausted to increase their knowledge and skill base in reporting and analytics concerning project management inputs based on Front-to-End framework. The outputs can be prepared as in-house development by administrative staff.

4. For future researchers and enthusiasts in the field of project management, they may enhance the scope and parameters of the study by utilizing a different data gathering instrument or checklist. They may also apply the insights and inquiry on project management to other kinds of industries, not just construction. This will allow them to have a deeper analysis on how Front-to-End framework may be utilized in actual setup. Likewise, these project management tools should include a detailed breakdown of all the cost associated with the project to provide a valid and reliable representation of the expected costs of a construction project.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study ensured that the ethical concerns was addressed properly. The researcher has requested for the consent of the respondents and ensured that the data and information that they provided are secured and were not used into other purposes aside from the research.

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